
From Classification to Regression: A Note on Deodata Predictors

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Abstract

Methods to turn classification algorithms into regression algorithms are described for deodata predictors. A sampling density compensation scheme is also proposed.

Keywords: regression, classification, density estimation, sampling density compensation

1 Introduction

The family of predictive methods described in [1], also referred to as "concurrent data predictors" or "deodata predictors", are used to provide a predictive measure for the target outcomes. The algorithms can be adapted for problem settings where the predicted outcome is continuous instead of categorical. This enables the adapted algorithms to perform regression and density estimation tasks.

The deodata algorithm family is subdivided in several groups. Of interest are the subgroups referred to as "delanga" (proximity) and "rasturnat" (swapped). A brief description of the deodata predictive algorithms follows.

2 Deodata Predictors

Unlike decision trees, deodata predictors evaluate attributes concurrently and not in sequence. From a conceptual point of view, lazy learning, online algorithm, and instance-based learning are all descriptions that apply to deodata predictors.

A common characteristic of deodata predictors is the comparison of the attribute values of the training data entries with those of the query.

The training data set can be viewed as tabular data where each row corresponds to a training entry. Each column corresponds to an attribute/feature. A target outcome, also referred to as class or label, is associated to each training entry. The query can be viewed as a list of attribute values ordered in the sequence of attribute columns in the training data table.

The comparison with the query results in the computation of an entry match score for each row of the training data set. The entry match score is an aggregation of several column match scores. The column match score measures the degree of similarity between a pair of attribute values. The paired attributes correspond to the query and the training entry, respectively.

In the simplest case, the column match score can be a value of either one (1) or zero (0) depending on whether the attribute values match or not. Also, the aggregation of the column match scores can be a summation. In here, these choices are made and the entry match score represents the number of attribute values that match with the query. In this simple implementation, the entry match score is equivalent to a Hamming distance or overlap measure.

The way the entry match score is used differs among the deodata algorithm subfamilies.

3 Deodata Delanga (Proximity Concurrent Predictor)

The basic operation of the delanga variant consists in searching for the set of training entries that have the largest possible entry match score. The resulting set of entries will be used for prediction. The relative frequency of the outcomes in the predictive set provides an indication of their likelihood. For classification, a majority rule can be applied to the predictive set.

4 Deodata Rasturnat (Swapped Concurrent Predictor)

In the rasturnat variant, the roles of the entry match scores and the outcome occurrences are swapped. The algorithm's operation consists in aggregating each entry's score to the corresponding outcome. The accumulated scores of each outcome provide a predictive measure of its likelihood.

The operation of the rasturnat variant involves an additional step, the evaluation of a transformation function. This function is applied to the entry match score and induces nonlinearity into the resulting entry transform score. This result is aggregated to the corresponding target outcome score.

5 Delanga Regression

If the target outcome is a continuous value instead of categorical, the algorithm changes as follows. The predictive set of outcomes with the highest entry match score is selected and becomes the champion predictive set. The output value associated to the query is computed as the average of the training entry outcomes present in the champion predictive set.

The procedure is illustrated by an example in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Deodata delanga regression example

More formally, the following definitions are used:

M_{TEN} ,	the number of entries in the training data set;
N_{TAC} ,	the number of attribute columns in the training data set;
$TT[m, n]$,	tabular training data matrix of size $M_{TEN} \times N_{TAC}$;
$q[n]$,	query vector of size N_{TAC} ;
$Y_{OUTC}[i]$,	the target outcome corresponding to row i in the training data table TT ;
$f_{TRANSF}()$,	the score transformation function (kernel);
$ems(q, i)$,	the entry match score for row i with respect to query q ;
$f_Y(q)$,	the function that calculates the regressed value corresponding to query q .

The following statement applies:

let $S_{CHAMP_Q} []$ be the champion index list corresponding to query q and containing K indexes to the best matching training entries. The regressed value is

$$f_Y(q) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{K-1} Y_{OUTC}[S_{CHAMP_Q}[i]]}{K} .$$

In the given numerical example the query entry is $q_X = ['a2', 'b1', 'c0', 'd1']$ and $f_{TRANSF}(x) = 2^x$. The corresponding entry match scores are

$$\begin{aligned} ems(q_X, 0) &= 3, & ems(q_X, 3) &= 3, \\ ems(q_X, 1) &= 0, & ems(q_X, 4) &= 1, \\ ems(q_X, 2) &= 1, & ems(q_X, 5) &= 3. \end{aligned}$$

The highest entry match score is 3, corresponding to entries at index 0, 3, and 5

$$S_{CHAMP_Q} [] = [0, 3, 5] .$$

The corresponding champion predictive set S_{TOP} contains

$$\begin{aligned} S_{TOP} &= \{ Y_{OUTC}[0], Y_{OUTC}[3], Y_{OUTC}[5] \} \\ &= \{ 31, 22, 23 \} . \end{aligned}$$

The regressed value is

$$\begin{aligned} f_Y(q_X) &= (31 + 22 + 23)/3 = 76/3 \\ &= 25.3333 . \end{aligned}$$

6 Rasturnat Regression

For the rasturnat variant, the algorithm changes as follows. For each row of the training data table, the entry transform score is computed. The value is multiplied with the entry's target output value and is added to the current output mixed total. Separately, the entry transform score is added to the current transform total. After all entries have been processed, the predicted output consists in the output mixed total divided by the transform total.

The operation is illustrated in Fig. 2 where the transformation function is a power of two.

Figure 2: Deodata rasturnat regression example

Let $ets(q, i)$ be the entry transform score for training entry i where

$$ets(q, i) = f_{TRANSF}(ems(q, i)) .$$

Let $S_{TOTAL}(q)$ be the transform total and let $S_{MIX}(q)$ be the output mixed total for query q

$$S_{TOTAL}(q) = \sum_{i=0}^{M_{TEN}-1} w_{ADJ}(i) \cdot ets(q, i) ;$$

$$S_{MIX}(q) = \sum_{i=0}^{M_{TEN}-1} Y_{OUTC}[i] \cdot w_{ADJ}(i) \cdot ets(q, i) ;$$

where $w_{ADJ}()$ is the adjusting factor for training entry i . In here it is a constant function returning one and acts only as a placeholder for other variants

$$w_{ADJ}(i) = 1 .$$

The regressed value is

$$f_Y(q) = S_{MIX}(q) / S_{TOTAL}(q) .$$

In the given numerical example

$$\begin{aligned} S_{TOTAL}(q_X) &= (2^3 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 2^3 + 2^1 + 2^3) \\ &= (8 + 1 + 2 + 8 + 2 + 8) \\ &= 29 , \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{MIX}(q_X) &= (31 \cdot 2^3 + 16 \cdot 2^0 + 34 \cdot 2^1 + 22 \cdot 2^3 + 15 \cdot 2^1 + 23 \cdot 2^3) \\ &= (31 \cdot 8 + 16 \cdot 1 + 34 \cdot 2 + 22 \cdot 8 + 15 \cdot 2 + 23 \cdot 8) \\ &= 722 . \end{aligned}$$

The regressed value is

$$f_Y(q_X) = 722/29 = 24.8965 .$$

7 Field Sampling Density

In [2] a variation of the rasturnat algorithm is described for cases where the training entries are viewed as field samples, or measurements, instead of field generating particles. A regression adaptation for this type of algorithm involves additional steps. A density compensation factor needs to be precalculated for each training entry. Fig. 3 illustrates the main part of the procedure. The transformation function is a power of two.

attribute						
A	B	C	D	ems	ets	
a2	b1	c2	d1	4	4	16
a1	b2	c1	d0	0	0	1
a1	b1	c1	d0	1	2	2
a0	b1	c0	d1	2	4	4
a0	b0	c0	d2	0	0	1
a2	b0	c0	d1	2	4	4
a2 b1 c2 d1 28						
attribute						
A	B	C	D	ems	ets	
a2	b1	c2	d1	0	0	1
a1	b2	c1	d0	4	4	16
a1	b1	c1	d0	3	8	8
a0	b1	c0	d1	0	0	1
a0	b0	c0	d2	0	0	1
a2	b0	c0	d1	0	0	1
a1 b2 c1 d0 28						
attribute						
A	B	C	D	ems	ets	
a2	b1	c2	d1	1	2	2
a1	b2	c1	d0	3	8	8
a1	b1	c1	d0	4	4	16
a0	b1	c0	d1	1	2	2
a0	b0	c0	d2	0	0	1
a2	b0	c0	d1	0	0	1
a1 b1 c1 d0 30						
attribute						
A	B	C	D	ems	ets	
a2	b1	c2	d1	2	4	4
a1	b2	c1	d0	0	0	1
a1	b1	c1	d0	1	2	2
a0	b1	c0	d1	4	4	16
a0	b0	c0	d2	2	4	4
a2	b0	c0	d1	2	4	4
a0 b1 c0 d1 31						
attribute						
A	B	C	D	ems	ets	
a2	b1	c2	d1	0	0	1
a1	b2	c1	d0	0	0	1
a1	b1	c1	d0	0	0	1
a0	b1	c0	d1	2	4	4
a0	b0	c0	d2	4	4	16
a2	b0	c0	d1	2	4	4
a0 b0 c0 d2 27						
attribute						
A	B	C	D	ems	ets	
a2	b1	c2	d1	2	4	4
a1	b2	c1	d0	0	0	1
a1	b1	c1	d0	0	0	1
a0	b1	c0	d1	2	4	4
a0	b0	c0	d2	2	4	4
a2	b0	c0	d1	4	4	16
a2 b0 c0 d1 30						

Figure 3: Density compensation calculation

Expressing the procedure in more detail:

let $tss[j]$ be the train similarity score corresponding to entry j

$$tss[j] = \sum_{i=0}^{M_{TEN}-1} ets(j, i) ;$$

let STS be the summation of the train similarity scores for all entries

$$STS = \sum_{i=0}^{M_{TEN}-1} tss(i) ;$$

let $STAVG$ be the average train score

$$STAVG = STS / M_{TEN} ;$$

and $dcf[j]$ is the density compensation factor for training entry j

$$dcf[j] = STAVG / tss[j] .$$

The density compensation factor will replace the adjustment factor in the rasturnat regression operation

$$w_{ADJ}(j) = dcf[j] .$$

Using the previous example, the numerical calculations are

$$\begin{aligned} tss[0] &= ets(0, 0) + ets(0, 1) + ets(0, 2) + ets(0, 3) + ets(0, 4) + ets(0, 5) \\ &= 2^4 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 2^2 + 2^0 + 2^2 \\ &= 28 , \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} tss[1] &= ets(1, 0) + ets(1, 1) + ets(1, 2) + ets(1, 3) + ets(1, 4) + ets(1, 5) \\ &= 2^0 + 2^4 + 2^3 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 \\ &= 28 , \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} tss[2] &= ets(2, 0) + ets(2, 1) + ets(2, 2) + ets(2, 3) + ets(2, 4) + ets(2, 5) \\ &= 2^1 + 2^3 + 2^4 + 2^1 + 2^0 + 2^0 \\ &= 30 , \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} tss[3] &= ets(3, 0) + ets(3, 1) + ets(3, 2) + ets(3, 3) + ets(3, 4) + ets(3, 5) \\ &= 2^2 + 2^0 + 2^1 + 2^4 + 2^2 + 2^2 \\ &= 31 , \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} tss[4] &= ets(4, 0) + ets(4, 1) + ets(4, 2) + ets(4, 3) + ets(4, 4) + ets(4, 5) \\ &= 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 2^4 + 2^2 \\ &= 27 , \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} tss[5] &= ets(5, 0) + ets(5, 1) + ets(5, 2) + ets(5, 3) + ets(5, 4) + ets(5, 5) \\ &= 2^2 + 2^0 + 2^0 + 2^2 + 2^2 + 2^4 \\ &= 30 , \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} STS &= tss[0] + tss[1] + tss[2] + tss[3] + tss[4] + tss[5] \\ &= 28 + 28 + 30 + 31 + 27 + 30 \\ &= 174 , \end{aligned}$$

$$STAVG = STS / M_{TEN} = 174/6 = 29 ,$$

$$\begin{aligned} dcf[0] &= 29/28 = 1.0357 , \\ dcf[1] &= 29/28 = 1.0357 , \\ dcf[2] &= 29/30 = 0.9666 , \\ dcf[3] &= 29/31 = 0.9354 , \\ dcf[4] &= 29/27 = 1.0740 , \\ dcf[5] &= 29/30 = 0.9666 . \end{aligned}$$

Using the density compensation factors it follows

$$\begin{aligned} S_{TOTAL}(q_X) &= (1.0357 \cdot 2^3 + 1.0357 \cdot 2^0 + 0.9666 \cdot 2^1 + 0.9354 \cdot 2^3 \\ &\quad + 1.0740 \cdot 2^1 + 0.9666 \cdot 2^3) \end{aligned}$$

$$= 28.6185 ,$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\text{MIX}}(q_X) &= (1.0357 \cdot 31 \cdot 2^3 + 1.0357 \cdot 16 \cdot 2^0 + 0.9666 \cdot 34 \cdot 2^1 \\ &\quad + 0.9354 \cdot 22 \cdot 2^3 + 1.0740 \cdot 15 \cdot 2^1 + 0.9666 \cdot 23 \cdot 2^3) \\ &= 713.8584 . \end{aligned}$$

The regressed value is

$$\begin{aligned} f_Y(q_X) &= 713.8584 / 28.6185 \\ &= 24.9439 . \end{aligned}$$

8 Conclusion

Methods to adapt deodata algorithms for regression were presented. The resulting algorithms can be applied also in other areas like density estimation. A sampling density compensation scheme has also been proposed for nonuniform sampling settings.

References

- [1] Alb, C. (2021). Collapsing the Decision Tree: the Concurrent Data Predictor. arXiv preprint arXiv:2108.03887. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33413.06880>
- [2] Alb, C. (2022). Accuracy Convergent Field Predictors. arXiv preprint arXiv:2205.03712. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30987.16165>